

THE LEVEL OF VITAMIN D, ADIPONECTIN, RENAL FUNCTIONS AND LIPID PROFILE IN A SAMPLE OF TYPE 2 DIABETIC PATIENTS

Qamar Adnan Mohamed Mahdi

Al _karkh University of Science Department of microbiology

Maryam Louay Kazem Mahdi

University of Baghdad Department of Biosciences

Mohammed Abdallah Madah Mutar

University of Mustansiriyah College of Science Department of Biosciences

Amina Atheer Mohammed

University of Mosul Collage of Sciences Department of biology

Zahraa Jaafar Resen Jouda

University College of Madenat Al-Elem Department of biology

Abstract: Vitamin D and adiponectin were low in DM patients, Vitamin D decreased with age, while adiponectin level increased with age. The BMI was increased in patients than control. Kidney function test in patients were more than control except uric. Lipid profile serum in patients increased than control except HDL was in patients group less than control group.

1. Introduction:

Diabetes is defined as a group of metabolic diseases characterized by hyperglycemia due to impaired secretion and/or insulin action or both. Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) is a heterogeneous group of disorders resulting from the combination of genetic predisposition, behavioral, nutritional, and environmental risk factors (**Organization, 2017**). It is a very common endocrinal disorder affecting a majority of the world population and reaching to epidemic proportions in some countries (**Guari-guata et al., 2014**). Diabetes mellitus is characterized by several defects in the regulation of carbohydrate, fat or protein metabolism, or all of the above (**Gil et al., 2018**), because of this, it is characterized by hyperglycemia, hyperlipidemia, and negative nitrogen balance. The metabolic deregulation may be associated with secondary damage to multiple organ systems, especially the nerves, eyes, blood vessels and kidneys (**Christ-akos, 2017**).

Vitamin D (VD) has been shown to prevent increases in glucose concentration and insulin resistance, enhance insulin sensitivity and reduce systolic blood pressure in type 2 diabetic patients (**Gil et al., 2018**). Many studies showed an association or a link between low serum 25-hydroxyvitamin D₃ (25(OH)D₃) concentration and an increased risk for the metabolic syndrome and type 2 diabetes outcomes (insulin resistance, insulin secretion, and its replenishment improves β -cell function and glucose tolerance) (**Christakos,**

2017) (Tao et al., 2017). Moreover, certain allelic variations in the vitamin D receptor (VDR) and vitamin D-binding protein (DBP) might influence glucose tolerance and insulin secretion (**Szymczak-Pajor & Śliwińska, 2019**), thus contributing to the genetic risk for type 2 diabetes. As vitamin D modulates insulin receptor gene expression and insulin secretion, it is an interesting environmental candidate for T2DM Pathogenesis and development (**Wang et al., 2018**).

Adiponectin, also known as adipocytes complement-related protein of 30 kDa), a hormone origin that is involved in the homeostatic control of circulating glucose and lipid levels (**Banerjee et al., 2017**). Reduced adiponectin levels are documented in obese, insulin resistant, and type 2 diabetes-afflicted patients, adiponectin and 25 hydroxyl vitamin D levels regulating food intake, energy metabolism, glucose and lipid metabolism and body weight have been reported in the pathogenesis of Prediabetes and T2DM (**Al Shehri, 2017**). The liver plays an important role in carbohydrate metabolism as it has the capability to store glucose as glycogen and synthesize glucose from non-carbohydrate sources, increased activities of liver enzymes such as aspartate aminotransferase (AST) and alanine aminotransferase (ALT) are indicators of hepatic-ellular injury and also associated with insulin resistance (**Sheng et al., 2018**), metabolic syndrome and type 2 diabetes. Diabetic patients may have induced dyslipidemia. Dyslipidemia is *elevation* of plasma cholesterol, triglycerides (TGs), or both, or a low HDL cholesterol level that contributes to the development of atherosclerosis. Causes may be primary (genetic) or secondary. Diagnosis is by measuring plasma levels of total cholesterol, TGs, and individual lipoproteins. Treatment involves dietary changes, exercise, and lipid-lowering drugs (**Lazo-Porras et al. 2016**).

Underlying biochemical and hematological changes in T2DM patients may lead to the development of long-term complications and poor quality of life or death. Therefore, it is critical to follow up and monitor carefully biochemical and hematological parameters in diabetic patients (**Abbas, 2017**).

3. Materials and Methods

3.1 Subjects and Study design

Blood samples were collected from 180 participants who were visited Specialized Center for Endocrinology and Diabetes for the period from December 2019 to February 2020. The samples were (180) divided into two groups first group (120 patient with type 2 diabetes divided into 2 groups (60 males and 60 females) their age rang was (35- 65 years) and second group 60 subjects as healthy control) divided into 2 groups (30 males and 30 females)their age rang was (32 -65) years.

In this study special questionnaire was prepared and filled by the participants, the questionnaire included descriptive information for each patient (name, gender, age, weight, height and history duration of DM), The Body Mass Index (BMI) was calculated for all the study group (weight (kg)) / height (m)²] as in table (2:2) (**Kramer et al., 2013**).

3.2 Sample Collection

About 5ml of venous blood was collected from each participants (patient with type 2 diabetes and healthy control) and kept in plain tube and left to clot. Then serum was separated by centrifugation for 5 minutes. Serum was divided into separate plain tube (500 micro litter) volumes and all were labeled with the name and number then put into storage at (-20°C) until the time of test. Before start working the samples were thawed properly at room temperature.

3.3 Materials

In this study the materials used included tools, instruments, kits.

3.3.1 Tools

Table 3-1 shows all Laboratory tools used in this study

Tools	Made	Company
Automatic pipet	Germany	Median
Can tubes	Germany	Median
Disposable pipet tips	China	Clean Med
Plain tubes	Germany	Median
Timer	China	Clean Med

3.3.2 Instruments

Table 3-2 Shows list of instruments

Instruments	Made	Company
Centrifuge	Germany	Hettich
Flexor- EL80	South Africa	Vitalab
Lipidocare analyzer	Korea	SD Biosensor
Reader automated Elisa	Germany	Human
Refrigerator	Turkey	Beko
Spectrophotometer PD-303UVApel	USA	Apel
Water bath	China	XMTE

3.3.3 Kits

Table 3-3 list of Kits

Kits	Made	Company
Creatinine kit	South Africa	Vitalab
Glucose kit	Spain	Biosystem
Human Vitamin D3 Elisa kit	USA	Ray biotech
Human Adiponectin Elisa k	USA	Cusabio
Standard lipidocare lipid test strip	Korea	SD Biosensor
Uric acid kit	South Africa	Vitalab
Urea kit	South Africa	Vitalab

3.4 Methods

3.4.1 Human Vitamin D3 (VD3) kit.

Detection principle of Human Vitamin D3 (VD3) ELISA kit: This experiment uses a double-sandwich ELISA technique and the ELISA Kit provided is typical. The pre-coated antibody was a human VD3 monoclonal antibody and the detecting antibody was a polyclonal anti-body with biotin labeled. Samples and biotin labeling antibody were added into ELISA plate wells and washed out with PBS or TBS. Then Avidin – peroxidase conjugates were added to ELISA wells in order; Use TMB substrate for coloring after reactant thoroughly washed out by PBS or TBS, TMB turns into blue in peroxidase catalytic and finally turns into yellow under the action of acid. The color depth and the testing factors in samples were positively correlated.

Assay procedure

1. Samples or different concentration of human VD3 standard samples to corresponding wells (100µl for each well), Ong/ml well were added then should be filled with standard diluents. Reaction well was sealed with adhesive tapes and was hatched in incubator at 37 ° C for 90 min.
2. Biotinylated human VD3 antibody liquid 30min was prepared in advance.
3. Elisa plate was washed two times
4. Biotinylated human VD3 antibody liquid was added to each well (100µl for each reaction ,wells were sealed with adhesive tapes and were hatched in incubator at 37 ° C for 60 min.
5. Enzyme conjugate liquid 30min was prepared in advance.
6. Elisa plate was washed three times.
7. Enzyme conjugate liquid was added to each well except blank wells (100µl for each). reaction wells were sealed with adhesive tapes and were hatched in incubator at 37°C for 30 min.
8. Elisa plate was washed five times.
9. Color Reagent liquid(100µl)was added to individual well (also into blank well)and was hatched in dark incubator at 37°C. When the color of the high concentration of standard curve became darker and color gradient appeared, the hatching can be stopped, The chromogenic reaction should be controlled within 30 min.
10. Color Reagent C (100µl) was added to individual well (also into blank well),the well was mixed. OD (450nm) was read within 10 min.

Normal range of:

25 hydroxy vitamin D3	Deficient	Less than	20
	Insufficient	Less than	30
	Sufficient	30 – 100	ng/ml
	Potential toxicity	<100	

Result determination

1. The OD value of each sample and specimen should be minus that of blank well (if not, the standard curve of zero well should intersect at Y axis).

2. The standard curve was drawn manually. Concentration value of samples as abscissa and OD readings as vertical coordinate was taken. Smooth line to connect each coordinate point of Standard sample was used. The concentration of samples found by checking sample OD reading. It was recommended to employ the professional curve software to analyze and compute the result.
3. If the sample OD was higher than the upper limit of a standard curve, the sample should be diluted and the experiment rerun when calculating the unknown the result was multiplied by dilution factor.

3.4.2 Human Adiponectin (ADP) kit.

PRINCIPLE OF THE ASSAY

This assay employs the quantitative sandwich enzyme immune-assay technique, Antibody specific for ADP has been pre-coated onto a micro plate, Standards and samples were pipetted into the wells and any ADP present was bound by the immobilized antibody. After removing any unbound substances, a biotin - conjugated antibody specific for ADP was added to the wells. After washing avidin conjugated Horseradish Peroxidase (HRP) was added to the wells, Following a wash to remove any unbound avidin - enzyme reagent. A substrate solution was added to the wells and color develops in proportion to the amount of ADP bound in the initial step. The color development was stopped and the intensity of the color was measured.

Detection range 1.562 - 100 ng/ml

Assay procedure

1. All reagents, working standards, and samples were prepared as illustrated in the previous sections.
2. The Assay Layout Sheet was referred to determine the number of wells to be used , any remaining wells and the desiccant back were put into the pouch and sealed the Ziploc, the unused wells were stored at 4°C.
3. 100µl of standard and sample were added per well and covered with provided adhesive strip after that were incubated for 2 hours at 37°C. A plate layout was provided to record the assayed standards and samples.
4. Liquid of each well was removed without washing.
5. 100µl of Biotin-antibody (1x) was added to each well and covered with a new adhesive strip then Incubated for 1 hour at 37°C. (Bio-tin-antibody (1x) may appear cloudy. Room temperature was warmed up and mixed gently until the solution appeared uniform).
6. Each well was aspirated and washed, repeated the process two times for a total of three washes. Washing by filling each well with Wash Buffer.(200µl) a squirt bottle was used, multichannel pipette, mani-fold dispenser or auto washer, and let it stand for 2 minutes. The liquid which was completed and removed at each step was essential for good then any remaining wash Buffer was removed by aspirating or decanting after the last wash. The plate was inverted and blotted it against clean paper towels.
7. HRP-avidin (1x) 100µl was added to each well. Micro titer plate was covered with a new adhesive strip and Incubated for 1 hour at 37°C.
8. The aspiration / wash process was repeated for five times as in step 6.
9. TMB Substrate 90µl was added to each well and incubated for 15-30 minutes at 37°C. (should be Protected from light).
10. Stop Solution 50µl was added to each well and gently tapped the plate to ensure thorough mixing.

11. The optical density of each well was determined within 5 minutes, using a micro plate reader set to 450 nm. If the wavelength correction was available, set to 540 nm or 570 nm. Subtract readings at 540 nm or 570nm from the readings at 450 nm. This subtraction to be corrected for optical imperfections in the plate. Readings made directly at 450 nm without correction may be higher and less accurate.

3.4.3 Detection of Glucose.

blood sugar was measured manually by spectrophotometer. 1.0ml reagent A and 10µl of standard were added in labeled test tubes, and 1.0 ml reagent and 10µl of serum were added in the test tube then mixed thoroughly after that incubated the tubes for 10 minutes room temperature (16-25°C) or for 5 minute at 37°C. The absorbance (A) of the standard and the sample was measured at 500 nm the color was stable for at least 2 hours.

Normal range of:

Fasting Blood Sugar (65- 110) mg/dl

3.4.4 Detection of Renal Function

Renal function test included (Urea, Creatinine, Uric acid) was tested by automated device Flexor-EL80. (500micron) serum was added in cuvette and incubated for 5 minute then the result was read.

Normal range of:

Urea (15-40) mg/dl

Creatinine (0.9-1.3) mg/dl

Uric acid (3.5 – 7.2) mg/dl

3.4.5 Detection of lipid profile.

Lipid profile test was included (Total cholesterol. Triglyceride, HDL, LDL, VLDL) were tested by automated device Lipidocare analyzer. 35µl of serum was added to lipidocare lipid test strip, in about three (3) minutes, the result appeared on the screen.

Normal range of:

Total Cholesterol (140- 250) mg/dl

Triglyceride (60- 170) mg/dl

HDL (40-70) mg/dl

LDL (65- 178) mg/dl

3.5 Statistical analysis:

Data were revised, coded, and analyzed using the “Statistical Pack-age of Social Science (SPSS) version 26.0.

1. For presentation of data using:

- ✓ Mathematical presentation method (Mean and Stander Deviation).
- ✓ Graphical presentation (Bar graph).

2. For analysis of data using:

- ✓ Independent sample t-test.

The comparison of significant (p-value) in any test was considered as:

P-Value of garter than 0.05 ($P>0.05$) was Non-statistically significant (NS).

* P-Value of less than 0.05 ($P<0.05$) was statistically significant (S).

** P-Value of less than 0.01 ($P<0.01$) was highly statistically significant (HS).

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 The level of Vitamin D&Adiponectin for patients and control groups

Table (4.1) The mean value of Vitamin D for patients and control groups was (14.50 ± 11.62 ng/ml) and (34.05 ± 6.51 ng/ml) respectively with a highly significant difference $P<0.01$ between them. In case of Adiponectin, control group was 20.83 ± 22.71 ng/ml, and in patients 12.24 ± 4.63 ng/ml with a highly significant difference $P<0.01$ between them. These research results in agreement with (Boulos and Geraghty, 2020) which found that a possible causal relationship between vitamin D deficiency and type 2 diabetes should be proven by randomized clinical trials showing that either type 2 diabetes can be prevented or insulin release and insulin sensitivity can be improved by vitamin D supplements (Lips *et al.*, 2017; Zhao *et al.*, 2021). The reason for this that vitamin D supplementation for 6 months significantly increased peripheral insulin sensitivity and β -cell function, suggesting that it may slow metabolic deterioration in this population (Swart *et al.*, 2018). Adiponectin decrease in DM because adiponectin is a fatderived hormone that appears to play a crucial role in protecting against insulin resistance/diabetes and atherosclerosis. Decreased adiponectin levels are thought to play a central role in the development of type 2 diabetes, obesity and cardiovascular disease in humans as the production of endogenous adiponectin is impaired as an effect of obesity and related pathologies, a practical therapeutic approach is to use pharmacological or [dietary interventions to restore the capacity of adipose tissue in secreting adiponectin also lower levels of adiponectin further contribute to peripheral insulin resistance in obesity)Ghoshal & Bhattacharyya, 2015(. **These results were in agreement with** (Achari & Jain, 2017).

Table (4.1): Comparison between study groups [Patients and Con-trol] according to VD &Adiponectin

Group		Mean± Std.	t-test	P-Value	(CS)
Control(n=60)	VIT.D3 ng/ml	34.05 ± 2.51	12.110	.000	$P<0.01$ (HS)
Patients(n=120)		14.50 ± 1.62			
Control(n=60)	Adiponectin ng/ml	20.83 ± 3.71	2.896	.004	$P<0.01$ (HS)
Patients(n=120)		12.24 ± 3.63			

Figure (4-1) Comparison between study groups [Patients and Control] according to VD & Adiponectin.

4.2 Vitamin D level and Age characteristics of patients and control

The study included 120 patients and 60 healthy control. Patients age range were (30 – 60) years as shown in Table (4.2). The age was divided into 4 groups (30-39), (40-49), (50-59) and (≥ 60) years with a mean \pm SD for age was (37.13 \pm 2.48), (44.09 \pm 2.88), (53.22 \pm 2.71) and (62.33 \pm 2.18) respectively. While mean \pm SD for VD value was (16.47 \pm 12.07ng/ml), (13.67 \pm 12.35ng/ml), (10.20 \pm 4.94ng/ml) and (8.95 \pm 5.28 ng/ml) respectively. The results in table (4-1) showed that VD value was decreased with increasing age and with a highly significant difference $p < 0.01$ between each age this is in agreement with (Barnard & Colón-Emeric, 2010). That is because older adults are at risk for lower levels of vitamin D as a result of decreased cutaneous synthesis and dietary intake of vitamin D. Epidemiologic evidence indicates an association between low levels of vitamin D and diseases associated with aging such as cognitive decline, depression, osteoporosis, cardiovascular disease, hypertension, type 2 diabetes, and cancer (Obata *et al.*, 2013).

Table (4-2): Vitamin D (ng/ml) concentration in Patients group in different Age group

Patients group	N	Mean \pm Std.	t-test	P-Value	C.S
Age(30-39) year	30	37.13 \pm 2.48	13.286	.000	P<0.01(HS)
VD ng/ml		16.47 \pm 2.07			
Age(40-49) year	30	44.09 \pm 2.88	16.663	.000	P<0.01(HS)
VD ng/ml		13.67 \pm 1.35			
Age(50-59) year	30	53.22 \pm 2.71	22.595	.000	P<0.01(HS)
VD ng/ml		10.20 \pm 1.94			
Age (≥ 60) year	30	62.33 \pm 2.18	26.711	.000	P<0.01(HS)
VD ng/ml		8.95 \pm 2.28			

Figure (4-2) Vitamin D (ng/ml) concentration in different Age group of diabetic subjects

4.3 The level of Adiponectin in Patients group and Age Groups

Table (4.3) Shows the results in this study for Adiponectin value were increased with increasing age respectively (15.98 ± 17.02 ng/ml), (18.00 ± 19.39 ng/ml), (19.70 ± 23.26 ng/ml), (24.85 ± 26.11 ng/ml) with a high significant difference < 0.01 between the ages. These results were in agreement with (Chen *et al.*, 2013). whom they found that Serum adiponectin levels increased with increasing age of healthy subjects and in patients with diabetes, in both men and women. Serum adiponectin levels were significantly and positively associated with age in healthy subjects and in patients with diabetes. This association is independent of renal function, body fat status, glucose metabolism and lipid profiles (AlQuaiz *et al.*, 2018). Through middle or early old age (e.g., 40–65 years of age), body mass and body fat percentage increase in both men and women. This age-related increase in adiposity has been suggested to underlie reduced insulin sensitivity with age (Karakelides *et al.*, 2010).

Table (4.3): Adiponectin concentration different Age Groups of Diabetes patients.

Patients group	N	Mean±Std.	t-test	P-Value	C.S
Age(30-39) year	30	37.13 ± 2.48	2.773	.000	P<0.01(HS)
Adiponectin ng/ml		15.98 ± 2.02			
Age(40-49) year	30	44.09 ± 2.88	11.073	.028	P<0.05(S)
Adiponectin ng/ml		18.00 ± 1.39			
Age(50-59) year	30	53.22 ± 2.71	8.241	.001	P<0.01(HS)
Adiponectin ng/ml		19.70 ± 2.26			
Age(≥ 60) year	30	62.33 ± 2.18	5.515	.000	P<0.01(HS)
Adiponectin ng/ml		24.85 ± 1.13			

Figure (4-3) Adiponectin level among diabetic Patients with various Age Groups (year).

4.4 The Level of VD & Adiponectin in Patients group in male and female

Table (4.4) show the value of VD between male (14.42 ± 11.37) and female (14.57 ± 11.95) and for adiponectin (20.74 ± 22.51) for male and (20.90 ± 23.10) for female and showed no significant difference between male and female $P > 0.05$. These results are not in agreement with (Wang *et al.*, 2010). Whom they found that adiponectin in mean and younger adults had a higher prevalence of vitamin D deficiency compared to older participants and females (McGrath *et al.*, 2010). This is because different variants in the loci of genes (such as DHCR7, CYP2R1, CYP24A1, and GC) that are responsible for vitamin D synthesis, hydroxylation, and transport, as well as VDR gene polymer-phisms, may be associated with the risk of vitamin D deficiency. Most tissues and cells in the body contain VDR. Following the genomic pathway in cells the active form of vitamin D binds to VDR and forms a complex. In the nucleus, this complex heterodimerizes with the retinoic acid x-receptor and affects the transcription of vitamin D-dependent genes. VDR is a nuclear transcription factor and has similarities to steroid and thyroid hormone receptors. It is encoded by the VDR gene located on chromosome 12 at position 13.11. Also, the table showed no significant difference between them $P > 0.05$ (NS) Adiponectin value between male and female it showed, decrease of adiponectin levels associated with increased androgen levels found in boys who were initiating puberty (Cui *et al.*, 2010; Bhupathiraju & Hu, 2016).

Table (4.4): Comparison between the value of VD & Adiponectin in Patients according their gender .

	Sex	n	Mean \pm Std.	t-test	P-Value	C.S
VD ng/ml	Male	59	14.42 ± 1.37	0.070	.944	$P > 0.05$ (NS)
	Female	61	14.57 ± 1.95			
Adiponectin ng/ml	Male	59	20.74 ± 2.51	0.038	.970	$P > 0.05$ (NS)
	Female	61	20.90 ± 3.10			

Figure (4-4) Vitamin D and Adiponectin in diabetic Subjects according to their gender.

4.5 Body mass index of patients and control groups

Table (4-5) show the mean value for BMI of patients and control groups was $(31.85 \pm 5.74 \text{ kg/m}^2)$ and $(23.43 \pm 1.46 \text{ kg/m}^2)$ respectively as shown in table (4) with a highly significant difference $P < 0.01$ between control and diabetic patients. (Collaboration, 2010). study was in agreement with this study they found that individuals with $\text{BMI} \geq 30 \text{ kg/m}^2$ are at substantially heightened lifetime risk of diabetes, Having even moderately elevated BMI is associated with increased risk of developing DM complications (Gray *et al.*, 2015). The reason for this was the passage from obesity to diabetes is made by a progressive defect in insulin secretion coupled with a progressive rise in insulin resistance. Both insulin resistance and defective insulin secretion appear very prematurely in obese patients, and both worsen similarly towards diabetes. The more excess weight you have, the more resistant your muscle and tissue cells become to your own insulin hormone.)Metzl & Kirk-land, 2010(.

Group	Mean± td. kg/ m ²	P-Value	t-test	(CS)
Control(n=60)	23.43±1.46			
Patients(n=120)	31.85±2.74	.000	11.169	P<0.01 (HS)

Table (4.5): Comparison between Groups study Patients and Control according to BMI.

4.6 Level of vitamin D for the control group with normal weight and overweight

The mean value of vitamin D for the control group with normal weight and overweight was (35.04 ± 5.74) , (32.57 ± 7.39) respectively with no significant difference between them $P > 0.05$ (NS).

The accumulation of vitamin D in the adipose tissue might explain why obese people have low vitamin D in the blood. Vitamin D deficiency is associated with the presence of a cardio metabolic risk profile in

the obese. The researchers suggest that all overweight and obese people have their vitamin D levels less than normal weight (Vranić *et al.*, 2019). A study by found the same results with this study (Walsh *et al.*, 2017).

Table (4.6): Vitamin D level of control group with variable BMI.

BMI Levels	N	Mean±Std. (VIT.D3)	P-Value	t-test	C.S
Normal weight	36	35.04±3.74			
Over weight	24	32.57±2.39	.152	1.435	P>0.05 (NS)

4.7 Level of adiponectin for control group with normal weight and overweight

Table (4-7) Shows the mean value of adiponectin for control group with normal weight and overweight was (12.52±4.12), (11.05± 4.99) respectively with no significant difference between them P>0.05 (NS). These results in agreements with (Kuo & Halpern, 2011). Adiponectin plays a pivotal role in energy metabolism; concentration of adiponectin decreases in obesity and increases after weight loss. Moreover, adiponectin also acts as an insulin-sensitizing hormone in muscle and liver, lower levels of adiponectin further contribute to peripheral insulin resistance in obesity Adiponectin plasma levels was lower in obese subjects and inversely correlated with obesity (Gariballa *et al.*, 2019)

Table (4.7): adiponectin levels of Control group with variable BMI.

BMI Levels	n	Mean ±Std. Adiponectin	P-Value	t-test	C.S
Normal weight	36	12.52±3.12 ng/ml			
Over weight	24	11.05±2.99 ng/ml	.152	0.382	P>0.05 (NS)

4.8 The Level of kidney function in Patients and Control Groups

Table (4.8) Shows The mean of blood urea in patient and control (38.88±8.15mg/dl), (30.13±9.87mg/dl) respectively with highly significant difference P<0.01 between them. While the mean of creatinine in both patient and control was (0.95±0.28mg/dl), (0.71±0.27mg/dl) respectively with a highly significant difference P<0.01 between them, and the mean value of uric acid for patient and control was (5.44±1.23mg/dl), (5.08±1.25mg/dl) with no significant difference P>0.05 between them.

The high levels of sugar in the blood damage the millions of tiny filtering units within each kidney. This eventually leads to kidney failure. Over time, poorly controlled diabetes can cause damage to blood vessel clusters in the kidneys that filter waste from the blood. This can lead to kidney damage and cause high blood pressure. High blood pressure can cause further kidney damage by increasing the pressure in the delicate filtering system of the kidneys. Higher blood urea nitrogen is associated with increased risk of incident diabetes mellitus. Experimental evidence suggests that higher levels of urea may increase insulin resistance and suppress insulin secretion (Xie *et al.*, 2018).

An increased level of creatinine may be a sign of poor kidney function when the blood vessels in the kidneys are injured, kidneys cannot clean the blood properly. body will retain more waste product to the blood (Bamanikar *et al.*, 2016).

People with type 2 diabetes often have high levels of uric acid in their blood, which could be due to extra fat.)Y. Cui *et al.*, 2016).

Also, the High level of uric acid or hyperuricemia makes oxidative stress by inducing the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) which interferes the insulin signaling pathway, creates inflammatory state

that reduced the insulin sensitivity, blood glucose uptake and metabolism, also reducing the insulin production from pancreatic islet cells. (Ward-hana & Rudijanto, 2018)

Uric acid levels rise with increasing blood glucose concentrations in the normal and pre-diabetes population. However, in type 2 diabetes patients, uric acid levels tend to decline with increasing blood glucose concentrations because of this uric acid level did not increase (Toyama *et al.*, 2015).

Table (4.8): Comparison between Groups study Patients and Control according to the kidney function.

Group		Mean± Std.	P-Value	t-test	(CS)
Control(n=60)	BU mg/dl	30.13±3.87	.000	6.319	P<0.01 (HS)
Patients(n=120)		38.88±4.15			
Control(n=60)	Cr mg/dl	0.71±0.27	.000	5.589	P<0.01 (HS)
Patients(n=120)		0.95±0.28			
Control(n=60)	UA mg/dl	5.08±1.25	.067	1.840	P>0.05 (NS)
Patients(n=120)		5.44±1.23			

Figure (4-5): Comparison between Groups study [Patients and Control] according to the kidney function.

4.9 Level of lipid profile according to Patients and Control Groups

Table (4-9) show that the value of cholesterol in control was (194.90±36.55) while in patients was (252.40±48.07) with a highly significant difference between them P<0.01. The value of TG in control was (141.35±42.83) while in patients was (180.38±74.29) with a highly significant difference between them P<0.01. Also LDL in control was (87.77±33.14) while in patients was (106.53±52.84) with a highly significant difference between them P<0.01. While HDL in control was (40.60±17.60) while in patients was (37.63±11.62) with no significant difference between them P>0.05. VLDL value in control was (106.53±52.84) while in patients was (130.32±33.64) with a highly significant difference between them P<0.01 (HS). This is because diabetes was clearly associated with high cholesterol synthesis and with mildly elevated serum and lipoprotein triglyceride levels. Insulin-resistant fat cells release large amounts of free

fatty acids to the circulation, which are taken up by the liver. (*imonen et al., 2002*). A number of factors may contribute to the changes in lipid metabolism in patients with type 2 diabetes, including insulin resistance and/or relative insulin deficiency, adipocytokines (e.g. adiponectin), and hyperglycemia two factors may increase VLDL production in the liver: the return of more fatty acids due to increased actions of hormone-sensitive lipase (HSL) in adipose tissue and insulin actions directly on apoB synthesis (*Berglund et al., 2012*). Type 2 diabetes is associated with a cluster of interrelated plasma lipid and lipoprotein abnormalities, including reduced HDL cholesterol, a predominance of small dense LDL particles, and elevated triglycerides. These abnormalities occur in many patients increased level of LDL cholesterol levels (*Gordon et al., 2010*).

This is because in insulin resistance and type 2 diabetes, increased efflux of free fatty acids from adipose tissue and impaired insulin-mediated skeletal muscle uptake of free fatty acids increase fatty acid flux to the liver (*Ozder, 2014*). Moreover, some adipocytokines, such as adiponectin, may contribute to the development of diabetic dyslipidemia (*Vergès, 2015*).

Table (4.9): Lipid panel for diabetic patients and control group.

Group		Mean± Std.	P-Value	t-test	(CS)
Control(n=60)	Cho mg/dl	194.90±22.55	.000	8.156	P<0.01 (HS)
Patients(n=120)		252.40±11.07			
Control(n=60)	TG mg/dl	141.35±23.83	.000	3.766	P<0.01 (HS)
Patients(n=120)		180.38±33.29			
Control(n=60)	HDL mg/dl	40.60±12.60	.239	1.182	P>0.05 (NS)
Patients(n=120)		37.63±11.62			
Control(n=60)	LDL mg/dl	87.77±14.14	.013	2.512	P<0.01 (HS)
Patients(n=120)		106.53±24.84			
Control(n=60)	VLDL mg/dl	130.32±30.64	.026	2.242	P<0.05 (S)
Patients(n=120)		142.50±34.73			

5.1 Conclusions

In the light of the results obtained, the study concluded the following:

1. Vitamin D and adiponectin were low in DM patients .
2. Vitamin D decreased with age ,while adiponectin level increased with age .
3. The BMI was increased in patients than control.
4. Kidney function test in patients were more than control except uric .
5. Lipid profile serum in patients increased than control except HDL was in patients group less than control group.

5.2 Recommendations

Based on the conclusion arrived at, the study recommended the following:

1. It is recommended the routine screening of vitamin D status for patients with diabetes mellitus type 2 and healthy controls. Vitamin D supplementation may be an effective public health intervention means, to improve the vitamin D status of the population.
2. Measuring serum adiponectin with leptin, IL6 and the relationship between them should be studied.

3. To investigate the impact of vitamin D treatment in diabetic and the role of vitamin D on glucose homeostasis and resistin as an inflammatory marker, future studies should use highly sensitive measures of insulin sensitivity and β -cell serum markers as well as other inflammatory markers.

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